

KEY INDICATORS

With 1,859,842 hectares, Germany ranked No. 4 in the EU in 2022. In terms of organic area share, it was slightly above the EU average of 10.6%, with 11.2%. Between 2001-2022, organic farmland almost trebled but was still below the EU growth. Regarding organic retail sales, with 15,310 million euros, Germany held rank one in the EU in 2022 and rank 2 worldwide, after the United States. With 6.3%, its retail sales share was above the EU average but only half as high as that of Denmark (12%).

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

632,165 ha (3.7%)

1,859,842 ha (11.2%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

194%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

290,000 ha (2.5%)

834,000 ha (7.1%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

7,000 ha (3%)

26,970 ha (13.6%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

334,000 ha (6.7%)

995,000 ha (21%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

8,573 t (26.7%) (2021)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2019-2021

Producers (Share of Total)

14,702 (13.6%)

36,688 (14%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

41

Processors

4,652

21,981

Importers

395

1,944

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

2,700 M € (1.8%)

15,310 M € (6.3%)

Per Capita Consumption

32.8 €

181 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

467 %

Imports

N/D

449,303 t

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN GERMANY

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, BLE, Agrarmarktinformationsgesellschaft, Nic Lampkin, Stiftung Ökologie & Landbau

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN GERMANY

Source: Agrarmarktinformationsgesellschaft AMI, Arbeitskreis Biomarkt, ZMP

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

Although the headline organic area indicator R29 refers to 2.0 Mha or just over 12% of the UAA in Germany by 2027, the CAP SP details cover nearly 2.4 Mha, or 14.4 % of UAA, supported as organic, representing a more than doubling of the organic area supported in 2018. The total funding is 84% higher, resulting in an 11% reduction in expenditure per hectare.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	1,150 kha	2,384 kha (+107%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	6.9%	14.4% (+109%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	77%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	300 M€	553 M€ (+84%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	261 €	232 € (-11%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	2,374 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	4,935 M€	23.7%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	5,083 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	34,169 M€	6.9%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	190-364	209-520	375-1500	665-1625	750+
	2023	P2	210-609	240-550	415-1440	850-2240	850+
Change from 2019 to 2023			~ +30%	~ +10%	~ 0%	~ +30%	~ +33%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	189-273	189-273	300-550	665-975	675+
	2023	P2	190-284	220-314	375-680	850-1060	850+
Change from 2019 to 2023			~ 0%	~ +15%	~ +25%	~ +10-25%	~ +25%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		~ 0-30%	~ 10-100%	~ 25-150%	~ 0-60%	~ +10%
	2023		~ 10-100%	~ 10-100%	~ 10-100%	~ 0-100%	~ +0%

Range of values shown mainly due to differences between Federal States in Germany

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Although not strictly an action plan, the Federal Programme for Organic Agriculture introduced in 2001 contained many relevant elements, including a common national logo, an information portal for organic farming (oekolandbau.de), consumer information events and research, most of which are still operational today. Over time, many of Germany's Länder introduced their own action plans, with Federal action plans in 2017 and 2023.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2017-22	20% of UAA by 2020	N/D
Current Action Plan	2023-30	30% of UAA by 2030	30% of food in government institutions organic by 2027

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2017 - 2022)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Germany is about 21%. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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